

Strategic Minerals at Stake: U.S. Interest in Brazil's Subsoil ¹

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Fieldwork conducted by the authors in an open-pit niobium mine, Goiás, Brazil, 2025.

Representatives of the U.S. government have expressed interest in Brazil's strategic minerals ¹ as a bargaining tool following Washington's recent decision to impose a 50% tariff on Brazilian products ². This move underscores an increasingly

evident geoeconomic strategy: the United States is mobilizing trade policy to secure access to critical mineral inputs for sectors considered strategic, including the energy transition and artificial intelligence.

This raises key questions: What exactly are strategic minerals? Why are they so vital in the current global order — and why has Brazil emerged as a significant player in this landscape?

What Are Strategic Minerals and Why Do They Matter?

Although definitions vary across institutions and contexts, the [International Renewable Energy Agency](#)³ classifies strategic minerals — also known as critical minerals — as those essential for advanced technologies and the energy transition. These minerals typically share one or more of the following characteristics: highly concentrated production in a limited number of countries, technical or environmental challenges in extraction, or declining quality and availability of reserves.

While the specific list may change depending on the period and analytical approach, it generally includes cobalt, nickel, copper, lithium, and rare earth elements. These resources are indispensable for producing batteries, solar panels, wind turbines, electric vehicles, semiconductors, medical devices, defense systems, satellites, and high-performance digital infrastructure — cornerstones of both the global energy transition and the digital economy.

Renewable Energy: The New Driver of Mineral Demand

The demand for renewable energy has grown at an exponential rate. According to the [Energy Institute](#)⁴, all major global energy sources reached record highs in 2024, driven by surging [worldwide consumption](#)⁵. Between 2013 and 2022, solar and wind power attracted investments of [US\\$ 1.63 trillion](#) and [US\\$ 1.31 trillion](#)⁶, respectively, leading to capacity expansions of [1,817.6%](#)⁷ and [362.3%](#)⁸ during the period.

At the same time, the United States faces mounting competition from China, which has consolidated its leadership in renewable energy. Currently, China produces approximately [4.4 times more solar energy](#)⁹ and [three times more wind energy](#)¹⁰ than the U.S. This disparity raises geopolitical concerns: beyond its technological dominance, China also controls much of the global supply chain for the minerals underpinning these technologies.

Renewable energy sources also exhibit characteristics that intensify mineral dependency, [including lower energy density, shorter lifespans compared to conventional sources, and limited recycling potential](#)¹¹. According to the [International Energy Agency](#)¹², an onshore wind turbine may require up to nine times more minerals than a natural gas plant of equivalent capacity, while offshore wind projects can demand up to fifteen times more. Similarly, electric vehicles require up to six times more critical minerals than conventional cars, largely due to the need for large-scale batteries.

[Solar energy technologies are particularly mineral-intensive](#)¹¹. The United States already hosts an estimated [5 million solar installations, a figure projected to reach 10 million by 2030 and 15 million by 2034](#)¹³. While most installations are small-scale residential systems, [industrial projects often exceed one million panels each](#)¹⁴. Importantly, all these systems will require replacement after their [20 - 30 year lifespan](#)¹⁵, highlighting the [immense and ongoing mineral demand associated with the global energy transition](#)¹⁶.

The Mineral Chain Behind Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) constitutes another central axis of the current dispute. Recognized as one of the most transformative technologies of the 21st century, AI already generates approximately **US\$ 250 billion annually and is projected to reach US\$ 830 billion by 2030**¹⁷. Shortly after reassuming the presidency, Donald Trump announced a reform and investment package of **US\$ 500 billion**¹⁸ to strengthen the sector's infrastructure, developed in coordination with leaders of major AI companies.

Although often associated with the digital sphere, **AI depends on a vast and highly material infrastructure**¹⁹. Thousands of data centers — energy-intensive facilities housing servers, optical equipment, and cooling systems — are required to sustain its operation. These components rely heavily on specialized metals and minerals, **the majority of which are extracted from regions of the Global South**¹⁶.

Currently, the **United States hosts around 5,400 of the 12,000 operational data centers worldwide**²⁰, underscoring the strategic importance of stable and continuous access to mineral resources.

The Global Mineral Chessboard

China's dominance over critical mineral supply chains poses a growing challenge to the United States. The most emblematic case is that of rare earth elements — **a group of 17 metals essential for advanced applications**²¹ such as permanent magnets, sensors, optical systems, electronic components, and metallic alloys. In 2023, **China controlled 68% of global rare earth production**¹⁶, while the U.S. accounted for only 12%.

This imbalance has spurred a series of U.S. initiatives aimed at diversifying access to these resources. In May 2025, **Trump proposed an agreement to Ukraine**²² that offered preferential access to critical mineral supply contracts in exchange for support in the war against Russia. The following month, he signed a controversial pact with China, **conditioning the issuance of student visas for Chinese nationals on the export of rare earths**²³.

Brazil in the Dispute

Recent studies suggest that **Brazil may possess the world's second-largest reserve of rare earth elements**²⁴ — one of the very resources driving U.S. diplomatic and commercial offensives.

This growing U.S. interest in Brazil's strategic minerals positions the country directly within the geopolitical dispute. In a context where economic and technological supremacy increasingly depends on material infrastructures — ranging from renewable energy systems and electric vehicles to data centers — the Brazilian subsoil acquires heightened geoeconomic significance.

However, abundance does not equate to sovereignty. The mere possession of strategic natural resources does not guarantee development, social justice, or international leadership. The use of these minerals as bargaining instruments in foreign relations places Brazil at a critical crossroads: either remain a passive supplier of raw materials or assert itself as an active agent, capable of adding value, safeguarding national interests, and conditioning agreements on technological, environmental, and social commitments.

Transparency Statement

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